

MONOTONIC TENSION, FATIGUE AND CREEP BEHAVIOR OF 3D BRAIDED KD-I-SiC-FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER-DERIVED SiC-MATRIX COMPOSITES AT 1100°C AND 1300°C FOR COATED AND UNCOATED SPECIMENS

Xin Jing, Duoqi Shi, Xiaoguang Yang

School of Energy and Power Engineering, Beihang University,

Beijing 100191, China

Email: shdq@buaa.edu.cn

Keywords: Ceramic Matrix Composites; Strength; Fatigue; Creep; High Temperature;

ABSTRACT

Monotonic tension, fatigue and creep tests of a composite where a polymer derived silicon carbide (SiC) matrix has been reinforced with three-dimensional braided KD-I fiber were conducted in air at 1100°C and 1300°C. The tensile mechanical properties at high temperatures exhibit considerable degradation compared to that at room temperature. The damage at high temperature not only decrease the short-term properties, but also influenced the long-term behaviors such as fatigue and creep. The deformation behaviors at 1100°C and 1300°C were different in creep and fatigue tests. Whereas oxidation embrittlement controls damage evolution and failure mechanisms and coatings play an important role on enhance high temperature properties for these SiC/SiC composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs), particularly those containing braided or woven fiber preforms, are under development for high temperature applications as e.g. in aero engine components, rocket nozzles, and re-entry thermal protection systems[1]. To be utilized into these areas, the composites should exhibit superior long-term mechanical properties under high temperature and oxygen environment. A thorough understanding of high temperature mechanical performance of the composites is necessary for design and life prediction.

In general, the first generation Si-C-O fibers and carbon-rich interface in SiC/SiC-based composites possessed relative low oxidation resistance at elevated temperature in air, limiting the long-term performance of SiC-based CMCs. The oxidation embrittlement propagates through matrix cracking, reacting with fiber, interface and matrix. In order to overcome this drawback, glass phase in the matrix[2, 3], SiBC[4], glass sealant[5] and coatings[6] were applied on the composites to act as an oxygen diffusion barrier and make the composites exhibited good mechanical properties in air.

The creep and fatigue behavior of SiC/SiC composites have been widely investigated, especially for the composites contain woven preform. Zhu investigated creep and fatigue behavior of SiC fibers (Nicalon and Hi-Nicalon) reinforced CVI derived SiC matrix composites in air and argon at temperatures ranging from 1000°C to 1300°C [7]. Both creep and fatigue resistance of Hi-Nicalon/SiC [8] is similar to that of enhanced SiC/SiC [9], but much better than standard SiC/SiC [10]. Improving fiber and matrix properties are the routines to enhance the composites performance during fatigue and creep tests at elevated temperatures. The failure mechanism was due to slow crack propagation in the matrix of the SiC/SiC composites. The crack propagation of the composites is controlled by both the bridged fibers and the matrix. Morscher [11] studied fatigue and creep properties of a melt-infiltrated SiC matrix Sylramic-iBN fibers reinforced composites. Two regimes of strength degradation were analyzed. At high stress level oxidation induced growth of matrix crack controlled the failure, while at low stress level the failure was attributed to fiber degradation. The fatigue properties of polymer derived crystalline [SiC+Si₃N₄] matrix reinforced with Sylramic type fibers composites[12], CVI derived SiC matrix reinforced with Hi-Nicalon fibers composites [13] and SiC-B₄C multilayered matrix reinforced with Hi-Nicalon fibers composites[14] were evaluated in air and in steam at elevated

temperatures to investigate the environment effect on fatigue. Results revealed that the presence of steam caused noticeable degradation for the fatigue properties. The creep behaviors are different for a combination of different fibers and matrix. Recently research demonstrates that the porous matrix, for example the SiC matrix derived by PIP process, does not carry significant stress, which leads to higher creep strain rate compared to that contains CVI or MI matrix composites[15].

Recently, the National University of Defense Technology (NUDT) and Beihang University conducted a program to develop 3D CMC based on the SiC/SiC composite system for aerospace application. The CMC consists of KD-I (Si-C-O) fibers and polymer-derived ceramic (Si-C-O) matrix. Polymer infiltration and pyrolysis (PIP) is an attractive processing method because of its relative low cost and allowance of near-net-shape molding and fabrication. The monotonic tension, creep and fatigue properties are investigated at elevated temperature. The damage and failure mechanisms during the high temperature mechanical tests are discussed.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Material

The CMC, provided by the National University of Defense Technology (NUDT), were chosen for this study because of their potential use in high temperature structural applications as hot section components in advanced jet engines. The composites are based on the SiC/SiC system with KD-I fibers as reinforcement. The yarns consisting 1.2K fibers were braided into a 3D four directional preform. The fiber volume fraction was approximately 45%. The preform was surrendered to a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process to prepare a ~200 nm thick pyrolysed carbon (PyC) layer. Polymer impregnation and pyrolysis (PIP) process with a polymer precursor of liquid polyvinylcarbosilane(LPVCS) was adopted to dense the matrix. 14 cycles of impregnation and pyrolysis were repeated to reduce the composites porosity. The original densified preform was a flat plate of which the size is 130 mm×60 mm×4 mm. The tensile test specimens were cut by water-jet cutting machine. The overall specimen dimensions were roughly 127 mm×14 mm×4 mm and the central reduced section were 30 mm×6 mm×4 mm. For some specimens to be tested in elevated temperature, after machining to the geometry suitable for mechanical testing, a two-layer anti-oxidation coating was applied on the specimen surfaces to protect the composite against oxidation. The inner layer was mullite and the outer layer was erbium silicate. Both of the layer thickness was 0.1mm.

2.2 Mechanical Testing and Microstructure Observation

Mechanical properties of the CMCs at room and elevated temperatures were evaluated by monotonic tensile testing. All experiments were conducted under stress control in a servo-hydraulic SHIMADZU test machine. The monotonic tension, creep and fatigue tests was conducted following the general guidelines of ASTM standard C1275, C1359, C1337 and C1360 [16-19]. The specimens were gripped by edge load, passive grip interface and the alignment of the testing system was verified at the beginning of the test series. Strain was measured directly from the gage section of the sample using an Epsilon-3548 high temperature extensometer.

For elevated temperature test, an induction furnace was used to heat the entire reduced section of the samples. The temperature was monitored near the specimen surface with the aid of two thermocouple located at both ends of the gage section to guarantee that a uniform temperature distribution (to within ± 1 °C) exists in the entire 25mm gauge section. High-temperature tests were performed following a programed procedure to the test temperature. Heating rates from RT to 1100 °C were approximately 0.6 °C/s and reduced to 0.2 °C/s above 1100 °C until reach the specified test temperature. A subsequent equilibration time of 5 min was hold to confirm uniform temperature distribution in gage section. With the high thermal conductivity and small dimensions of the samples, it could be shown that this is sufficient time for a uniform temperature to be reached throughout the gauge section. The failed specimens were furnace-cooled at an estimated rate of 2 °C /s above 1000 °C. The total time spent at the test temperature was approximately 700s. The monotonic tensile tests were

conducted at room temperature, 1100 °C and 1300 °C for uncoated specimens. The coated specimens were only conducted at 1300 °C. Before and after the fatigue test, the microstructure and fracture surface of the specimens were observed using computed tomography (CT) and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructures and Monotonic Tension

The as received materials are firstly examined by the CT and SEM (Fig.1). The detail of braided preform structure can be found everywhere[20-22]. The CT micrograph shows that there are many pores in the matrix-rich area between yarns. The pores formed a narrow inter-yarn channel and separated each yarn.

Fig.1. Microstructure of the 3D braided SiC/SiC composites.

Tensile stress-strain behavior of the KD-I/SiC composites at 1100°C and 1300 °C is shown in Fig.2a. The stress-strain curves initiated with a linear response, followed by a non-linear behavior. The ultimate tensile stress (UTS) of composites with coating was considerably higher than that of the composites without coating and was close to the UTS at room temperature. Likewise the coating maintained the elastic modulus (70% of the RT modulus) of composites at 1300 °C, but the modulus for uncoated specimens dropped almost 55%. The proportional limits for each case at high temperatures were close and were determined to be 80MPa (~40% UTS). To obtain the hysteresis mechanical behavior, unloading-reloading tests were conducted at room temperature. The hysteresis loop curve shown in Fig.2b clearly indicates that the stiffness and proportional limit are damage dependent. Notice that the loading and unloading curves are almost linear and overlapped when the peak stress is 200MPa and the hysteresis loop width increase as the peak stress increase. However, the hysteresis loop width and permanent strain is negligible. The same phenomenon has also been found in woven-reinforced polymer-derived CMCs with strong interface of which the debond stress is 1500MPa[23]. It is believed that the strong interface hindering the fiber sliding and the debonding and sliding of yarns are responsible for these phenomenon. However, the carbon interface in these CMCs are relative weak compared with the baron coat. The debond stress is ~100MPa and the slip stress is

~5MPa at room temperature. The inter-tow debonding and fiber statistic break are considered as the main mechanism.

Fig.2. (a) Stress-strain response of the CMCs under monotonic tension (C means the coated specimen and U means the uncoated specimen). (b) Unloading and reloading curve of CMC in RT tension shows no obvious hysteresis loop and permanent strain.

3.2 Creep and Fatigue

Maximum stress vs cycles to failure plot for fatigue tests is shown in Fig.3a, which indicated that in air, the fatigue behavior of the composites was influenced by temperature and coating. The fatigue performance for the coated specimens decreased a little with increasing temperature from 1100 °C to 1300 °C. The fatigue run-out stress at 1100 °C was 60MPa, which was higher than 45MPa at 1300 °C. The influence of temperature on cycles to failure was not obvious, indicating that similar mechanisms controlled the fatigue life above 1100 °C. The coating prevented oxidation embrittlement effectively at 1300 °C, especially under high stress (>80MPa). For the coated specimens, the number of cycles to failure increased gradually with decreasing maximum stress. The fatigue run-out stress was 45MPa. However, for the uncoated specimens under a stress above 80MPa at 1Hz, the number of cycles to failure exhibited considerable reduction, which was not more than 10^3 . When the stress was not more than 63MPa, the cycles to failure was above 10^4 , similar to the fatigue life for the coated specimens. The fatigue run-out stress was 40MPa, which was close to that for coated specimens. The difference on fatigue behavior between uncoated and coated SiC/SiC composites at 1Hz indicated that the coating improved the resistance to the oxidation invasion, resulting in longer rupture time for the crack propagation.

Maximum stress vs time to failure plots for all the fatigue and creep tests are also shown in Fig.3b. The effect of loading frequency on fatigue performance was not obvious. Although in the S-N plot, the numbers of cycles to failure at 10Hz were increased compared to the data derived at 1Hz, the stress vs time to failure curves demonstrated that time to failure was similar between 1Hz and 10Hz.

Creep rupture behavior in Fig.3b were similar to the fatigue failure behavior. The temperature effect on strength degradation seemed to be also not significant between 1100 °C and 1300 °C for coated composites. Although the data is seen to have considerable scatter, it would appear that a change in creep strength degradation behavior for uncoated specimens occur in short-term region within 1000 sec. The difference in strength degradation behavior was not notable between uncoated and coated specimens tested at 1300 °C for long-term.

Fig.3. (a) Maximum stress vs cycles to failure plot and (b) maximum stress vs time to failure plot for KD-I/SiC composites at elevated temperatures. *Arrow* indicated that failure of specimen did not occur when the test was terminated.

During the fatigue cycles, several types of damage occurred and interacted, leading to the degradation of load-bearing capacity and ultimate failure. Typical evolutions of hysteresis response of the composites are shown in Fig.4a. In all tests, it is seen that strain ratcheting occurred and the permanent strain increased as cycle increased. This phenomenon should be probably attributed to the creep behavior (fiber dominated). Especially when the specimen was close to fail, the compliance, loop width and permanent strain increased dramatically. The stiffness reduction was attributed to many damage mechanisms including matrix cracking, slippage and break of the bridging fibers. Fig.4b shows the change in normalized modulus with fatigue cycles at 1300°C and 1Hz for coated composites. Generally as the fatigue stress increasing, the rate of modulus loss increased. It is noteworthy that modulus decreased gradually if the tests achieved run-out. Instead, when the composites were close to fail, the modulus drop accelerated. Usually the process for the dramatic modulus drop last for several hundreds of cycles until the composites failed.

Fig.4. (a) Stress-strain evolution and (b) modulus degradation of SiC/SiC composites under fatigue load.

Maximum tensile strains as function of loading time for fatigue and creep tests of coated specimens conducted under a stress of 80MPa at 1100°C and 1300°C are presented in Fig.5a. At same stress level, the maximum strain in fatigue tests were less than that in creep test and the material showed more creep resistance at 1100°C than that at 1300°C. For creep tests at 1100°C, after a short transient creep period, quasi-steady state creep regions were dominated. For creep tests at 1300°C, the transient creep dominated creep behavior. The difference of creep strain behavior corresponded to the SiC fiber creep mechanism. The fiber creep are more significant at 1300°C than at 1100°C.

Fig.5. (a) Maximum tensile strains as function of loading time for fatigue and creep tests of coated specimens conducted under a stress of 80MPa at 1100°C and 1300°C. (b) Fig.9. Creep strain rate at different time versus applied stress for the composites at 1300°C.

In many cases, steady state creep rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_{cr}$, under applied stress, σ , is represented by the power law equation:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{cr} = A\sigma^n \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (1)$$

where A is a dimensionless constant, n the stress exponent, Q the apparent activation energy, R the universal gas constant, and T the absolute temperature. The eq(1) was utilized to determine the stress dependence at 5×10^2 , 1×10^3 , 5×10^3 , 1×10^4 , 5×10^4 , and 1×10^5 s for specimens tested at 1300°C. The stress exponents, n, were determined from the $\log \dot{\epsilon}_{cr}$ vs $\log \sigma$ plots (Fig.5b). Values of n decreased slightly with increasing time and all of them were close to unity, indicating the creep deformations were controlled by Newtonian-type viscous flow. These stress exponents are similar to that for the creep of Nicalon fibers, indicating that the creep rate of the composites is controlled by fiber creep.

3.3 Microstructure Damage and Fracture

The fracture surfaces of this type of CMCs had two different regions. Due to oxidation damage, the exterior fiber tows on the perimeter of the specimen cross section exhibited little or no fiber pullout, while the interior fiber tows showed considerable amount of fiber pullout. The fibers in undamaged region were thought as ‘effective fibers’ that contribute to the composite ultimate strength [24, 15]. It could be possible to conclude that oxidation damage propagated in the composites gradually through the flat unbridged matrix crack plane and the specimens failed when the fiber bundles in the rest undamaged region could not sustain the external load. Most of the cracks were located in the fiber-free matrix region, arrested by the individual bundles of braided preforms. The tunneling cracks between fiber bundles made the stress redistribution, leading to fiber bear more load. Thus indicate that the fiber creep dominate the composites creep deformation behavior. Few cracks penetrated into fiber bundles in the direction normal to the stress direction, especially near the surface, because of oxidation embrittlement. This resulted in cracks developing with oxidation-assisted fiber failure occurring essentially in the fracture plane. That explained the fracture surface contains the crack growth zones with fiber failure and sudden fracture occurred by fiber pull-out. Fig.6 shows the cracks in the composites under 40MPa and 120MPa at 1300°C. The crack density was greater for 40MPa than that for 120MPa. The cracks for 40MPa were all bridged by fibers, but some cracks for 120MPa were unbridged. After examining the crack in other specimens, it could be concluded that at low stress, the long rupture time lead to denser crack distribution. However, as stress increased, more unbridged cracks were observed. The unbridged cracks were difficult to be observed for the specimens tested under medium stress level, except the crack leading to ultimate fracture. The matrix cracking evolution, therefore, should be not only depend on stress, but also influenced by time.

Fig.6. Cracks distribution in the specimens at 1300°C under a creep stress of (a) 40 MPa and (b) 120 MPa.

The anti-oxidation coatings played an important role on maintaining the mechanical properties of the SiC/SiC composites for short-term at elevated temperatures. As the creep time increase, the difference for coated and uncoated composites became smaller, including the creep strain rate and rupture time. The effect of coating degraded as the load and time increased. Fig.7(a) shows cracks were observed on the coating of the specimen which was tested for 30h at 1300°C under a very small load (not more than 10MPa). As the stress increased to 40MPa (Fig.7(b)), more cracks were observed. The cracks on coating corresponded to the cracks on the specimen surface (Fig.7(c)), and these cracks became bridged cracks when they propagated from surface to interior region (Fig.7(d)). At high stress level, the unbridged cracks appeared in the coating weak area. Some pieces of the coatings began to be peeled off (Fig.7(e)), leading to the area underwent more severe oxidation damage. The coating, therefore, could protect the composites effectively from oxidation ingress as long as the integrity was maintained. Once the oxygen invaded the composites, the mechanical performance of the SiC/SiC composites would decrease dramatically.

Fig.7 Cracks on coating for the specimens under (a) 10 MPa, and (b) 40 MPa for 30h at 1300°C. (c) Cracks on surface and (d) cracks near the surface of the specimens under 40 MPa at 1300°C. (e) cracks on specimen under 80 MPa at 1300°C.

4 CONCLUSION

The CMC consists of KD-I (Si-C-O) fibers and polymer-derived ceramic matrix. Monotonic tension, tensile creep, and tension-tension cyclic fatigue experiments were performed in air at 1100°C and 1300°C.

Both the elastic modulus and ultimate tensile stress (UTS) decreased as the temperature increased. All the stress-strain curves were similar which initiated with a linear response, followed by a non-linear behavior. Due to oxidation embrittlement at elevated temperatures, the matrix cracking and fiber degradation led to lower UTS. However, the coatings effectively prevented the oxygen ingress and maintained the composite performance.

Tension-tension fatigue behavior was studied considering the influences of temperatures, coatings and loading frequency. The fatigue life decreased with increasing stress. The influence of temperature and loading frequency on fatigue performance was not obvious. The presence of coatings improved the fatigue properties, especially at high stress level. Strain ratcheting and modulus drop were observed during fatigue test. The strain accumulation increased and modulus decreased with increasing stress. When the composites were about to fail, dramatic strain increase and modulus drop occurred because unbridged cracks propagated by penetrating oxidized fibers.

The behaviors of deformation in creep and fatigue tests were similar. The creep deformation for composites tested at 1100°C contained primary and secondary stage while the creep deformation for composites tested at 1300°C only exhibited primary stage. The rate of creep deformation is controlled by fiber bundles. The creep rupture behaviors were similar for coated specimens tested at 1100°C and 1300°C. The uncoated specimens exhibited poor rupture behavior under high-level stress.

Oxidation embrittlement controls the damage and failure of the composites in fatigue and creep tests. The failure is depend on the factor of unbridged crack propagation and fiber strength degradation. As the developing cracks penetrate into the fiber bundles, crack growth rates are limited by crack-bridging fibers, but fiber failure is promoted by oxygen ingress. Ultimate failure takes place when the area of the developing cracks attained the critical fraction of the test-piece cross-section required for sudden failure by fiber pull-out. Crack density increased with increasing stress and temperature. The coatings did not change the crack density. However, it played an important role in preventing bridged cracks turn into more dangerous unbridged cracks.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (NO. NSFC51275023).

REFERENCES

- [1] Narottam P. Bansal, Jacques Lamon, Ceramic Matrix Composites: Materials, Modeling and Technology, New Jersey: New Jersey, 2014.
- [2] Zhu, S., et al., Creep and Fatigue Behavior in an Enhanced SiC/SiC Composite at High Temperature. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1998. 81(9): p. 2269-2277.
- [3] Zhu, S., et al., Creep and Fatigue Behavior in Hi-Nicalon-Fiber-Reinforced Silicon Carbide Composites at High Temperatures. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1999. 82(1): p. 117-128.
- [4] Chermant, J.L., et al., The creep mechanism of ceramic matrix composites at low temperature and stress, by a material science approach. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2002. 22(14–15): p. 2443-2460.
- [5] Davies, I.J., et al., Case study of failure in a glass-sealed SiC/SiC-based composite creep tested at 1100 °C in air. *Materials Letters*, 2001. 48(3–4): p. 205-209.

- [6] Eaton, H.E. and G.D. Linsey, Accelerated oxidation of SiC CMC's by water vapor and protection via environmental barrier coating approach. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2002. 22(14–15): p. 2741-2747.
- [7] Zhu, et al., Monotonic tension, fatigue and creep behavior of SiC fiber reinforced SiC matrix composites: a review. *Composites science And Technology*, 1999(59): p. 833-851.
- [8] Zhu, S., et al., Creep and Fatigue Behavior in Hi-Nicalon-Fiber-Reinforced Silicon Carbide Composites at High Temperatures. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1999. 82(1): p. 117-128.
- [9] Zhu, S., et al., Creep and Fatigue Behavior in an Enhanced SiC/SiC Composite at High Temperature. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1998. 81(9): p. 2269-2277.
- [10] Mizuno, M., et al., Cyclic-Fatigue Behavior of SiC/SiC Composites at Room and High Temperatures. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1996. 79(12): p. 3065-3077.
- [11] Morscher, G.N., et al., Tensile creep and fatigue of Sylramic-iBN melt-infiltrated SiC matrix composites: Retained properties, damage development, and failure mechanisms. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2008. 68(15–16): p. 3305-3313.
- [12] Ruggles-Wrenn, M. and V. Sharma, Effects of Steam Environment on Fatigue Behavior of Two SiC/[SiC+Si₃N₄] Ceramic Composites at 1300 °C. *Applied Composites Material*: 2011.18(5): p. 385-396.
- [13] Ruggles-Wrenn, M.B., et al., Effect of frequency and environment on fatigue behavior of a CVI SiC/SiC ceramic matrix composite at 1200 °C. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2011. 71(2): p. 190-196.
- [14] Ruggles-Wrenn, M.B., et al., Fatigue behavior of a Hi-NicalonTM/SiC–B₄C composite at 1200 °C in air and in steam. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 2012. 534(0): p. 119-128.
- [15] Morscher, G.N., Tensile creep and rupture of 2D-woven SiC/SiC composites for high temperature applications. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2010. 30(11): p. 2209-2221.
- [16] ASTM, Standard Test Method for Monotonic Tensile Behavior of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Advanced Ceramics with Solid Rectangular Cross-Section Test Specimens at Ambient Temperature, in C1275 – 10. 2010.
- [17] ASTM, Standard Test Method for Monotonic Tensile Strength Testing of Continuous Fiber Reinforced Advanced Ceramics With Solid Rectangular Cross-Section Test Specimens at Elevated Temperatures, in C1359-11. 2011.
- [18] ASTM, Standard Test Method for Creep and Creep Rupture of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Advanced Ceramics Under Tensile Loading at Elevated Temperatures, in C1337-10. 2010.
- [19] ASTM, Standard Practice for Constant-Amplitude, Axial, Tension-Tension Cyclic Fatigue of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Advanced Ceramics at Ambient Temperatures, in C1360 – 10. 2010.
- [20] Pluvinage, Parvizi-Majidi and T.W. CHOU, Damage characterization of two dimensional woven and three dimensional braided SiC-SiC composites. *Journal Of Materials Science*, 1996(31): p. 232-241.
- [21] Chen, L., X.M. Tao and C.L. Choy, On the microstructure of three-dimensional braided preforms. *Composites Science and Technology*, 1999. 59(3): p. 391-404.
- [22] Li, D., et al., Finite Element Analysis of Mechanical Properties of 3D Four-Directional Rectangular Braided Composites Part 1: Microgeometry and 3D Finite Element Model. *Applied Composite Materials*, 2010. 17(4): p. 373-387.

- [23] Chawla, N., et al., High-Frequency Fatigue Behavior of Woven-Fiber-Fabric-Reinforced Polymer-Derived Ceramic-Matrix Composites. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1998. 81(5): p. 1221-1230.
- [24] Ogasawara, T., et al., Tensile Creep Behavior and Thermal Stability of Orthogonal Three-Dimensional Woven Tyranno™ ZMI Fiber/Silicon-Titanium-Carbon-Oxygen Matrix Composites. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 2002. 85(2): p. 393-400.